

IMI2 821520 - ConcePTION

ConcePTION

WP8 – Scientific Coordination, Project Management & Sustainability

D8.12 Reports from Advisory Board and Ethics Report Year 5

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Abstract

This deliverable contains the assessment, guidance, and recommendations from the members of the Advisory Board of ConcePTION on project activities and compliance of these activities with IMI regulations, ethics, and scientific standard procedures. It primarily focuses on the progress of the sustainability plans for the project in its fifth and final year.

The feedback provided by each of the members of the Advisory Board is primarily based on the presentations and discussions which took place during the Advisory Board meeting on 4 July 2024. Before this meeting, each Advisory Board member received the meeting report from the General Assembly Meeting, held three weeks in advance of the Advisory Board meeting on 13-14 June 2024, containing the presentation of the plans regarding sustainability.

The members of the Advisory Board agree that ethical standards for data collection, privacy protection and human participation are met in the ConcePTION project.

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Introduction to the Advisory Board report

The aim of this deliverable is to report to IMI2 on the assessment and recommendations provided by the Advisory Board in the fifth year of the project, primarily focused on the different Work Stream plans for sustainability of the project. The feedback provided by each member of the Advisory Board is based on the presentations and discussions which took place during the Advisory Board meeting on July 4, 2024, as well as the reading materials received from Project Management Office. The reading materials included the meeting report from the final General Assembly Meeting held on 13-14 June 2024, at De Bazel in Amsterdam, the Netherlands. The report included summaries of the presentations given, discussions held, and recommendations made, as well as all the slides from the meeting.

The Advisory Board members that were present at the meeting were:

1. Christina Chambers, Professor of Pediatrics, University of California San Diego.
2. Elizabeth Conover, Genetic Counselor/Pediatric Nurse Practitioner, University of Nebraska Medical Center.
3. Jan Piasecki, Assistant Professor of Philosophy and Bioethics, Jagiellonian University Medical College.
4. Matthews Mathai, Obstetrician-Gynecologists.
5. Sabine Straus, Chair of the Pharmacovigilance Risk Assessment Committee (PRAC), European Medicines Agency.

Recommendations from the Advisory Board Members

1. Work Stream 1: Pregnancy Study Network – Primary Data

LIFETIME aims to improve long-term primary data collection focused on *in utero* exposure to medicines, enabling the collection of uniform data across various countries. Neurodevelopment is a critical aspect of child health, yet surveillance initiatives are limited, primarily due to a lack of expertise and the high costs of follow-up. To address this, LIFETIME has established an expert collaborative network and created a standardized framework for longitudinal follow-up. The team developed protocols and agreements to combine data from different countries, expanding the scope of pharmacovigilance and making it routine.

The LIFETIME operational model works on two levels: a cost-effective screening level using multilingual questionnaires suitable for large populations, and an enhanced level with blinded, researcher-led assessments for high-risk, new, or rarely used medications. The efforts are aligned with existing data collection initiatives, supplementing it with LIFETIME's dual-level investigations. This approach allows for collection of neurodevelopmental data, standardized data collection, risk detections, investigation of medication exposure via breastfeeding, and build additional sub-cohort studies.

The LIFETIME framework currently includes four European centres, and has recruited over 1,200 mother-child pairs, standardized data collection, initiated expansion with pilot centres, and attracted interest from other centres, including UKTIS. The next step involves focusing on epilepsy and integrating the initiative into general pharmacovigilance frameworks at various centres. Epilepsy affects up to 50,000 pregnancies annually, with 70% requiring anti-seizure medications, some of which pose risks of birth defects or long-term disabilities in exposed babies. The LIFETIME team aims to address this data gap by building a comprehensive dataset of 2,200 mother-child pairs, ensuring 500 undergo enhanced evaluations, tracking outcomes until the children are 10 years old, and reporting the findings.

In the next six months, the pilot will be completed, and the protocol and findings will be published. The next step will be to incorporate the findings into clinical guidelines. Simultaneously, the LIFETIME team is working to establish a longer-term governance structure and funding scheme.

For the PowerPoint presentation, please see Annex 1 (page 19-24).

Recommendations, comments and questions from the Advisory Board

- **Chambers:** In the groups engaged in the initiative, it seems like some of them have access to participate for drugs that fit the criteria that are not seizure medications. Do you have partners positioned to do this for other drugs as well? **A:** Absolutely, yes. We are a network where organizations can join and propose new initiatives around other groups of medications and areas of concern. We chose to focus on the anti-seizure medication because of the momentum it currently has, but we do not want it to be the primary focus of the full network. That is why we have chosen for the two different streams.

- **Chambers:** Do you see a role for primary data collection in other instances where non-primary data collection has led to uproar about certain medications? **A:** Yes, that could be done through this network, and we would love to learn from and collaborate with you in this regard.
- **Mathai:** In collecting the information on early-child development, are interventions considered? **A:** Yes, at the end of the questionnaires it asks if the child has been referred to anybody, and if so, whether it was for an assessment or an intervention.
- **Sturkenboom:** Could you tell us something about the requirements for potential collaborative centers? **A:** The requirements are that centers should collect data as early on in pregnancy as possible and that the information can be conformed to our common data model. To be involved in the enhanced level, it requires more, as you will need access to this expertise in-country to carry out the assessments in the native language. Due to the sensitivity of the data collection, the number of datasets that we need are smaller. Therefore, we foresee our network including more screening centers than enhanced data collection centers. Additionally, we are seeking funding. All suggestions for both centers and funders are welcomed.
- **Chambers:** Advocacy on the regulatory side of these drugs could play a part in sourcing funding. **A:** We are speaking to different industry partners both in- and outside ConcePTION to see what their post-authorization neurodevelopment safety study requirements are, and we know that for primary data it is very little while secondary data has its limitations. With these partners, we hope to further brainstorm what we can do in Europe to make these requirements around neurodevelopment much more central of what is asked of companies.
- **Conovers** commends the work that is done by the Work Stream.

2. Work Stream 2: Pregnancy Study Network – Secondary Data

What Work Stream 2 aims to do in the next six months (until the end of IMI ConcePTION) is to define what learnings from the ConcePTION project can be reused for a continuation of the pipeline, as well as to change things where necessary. First, the ConcePTION FAIR catalogue was developed, which is currently being maintained by the VAC4EU project. The data is collected with 15 data access providers, and the aim is to extend beyond Europe. There is a ConcePTION EHR CDM (version 2.2), of which a lot of materials are available on the WikiPage. Next steps include an inventory of the algorithms to make them reusable and sustainable for the future. In terms of data quality, three levels of data checks (transforming data to the CDM, logical plausibility, and benchmarking) have been developed with over 600 indicators. This is an open-source tool, which will be further developed into software. Other analytical functions have been developed, which are all available on the [WikiPage](#). The pipeline itself transforms datasets from a local format into CDM format through five transformation steps, with a multidisciplinary approach.

The key priorities moving forward are data readiness, method readiness, infrastructure readiness, and people readiness. The team aims to include more data sources, train new DAPs, include available algorithms and phenotypes, collaborate with VAC4EU for readiness of tools, develop a quality management system, and create a list of people and organisations who can help this pipeline move forward in the future.

Moving forward we hope to liaise further with pregnant and lactating women; engage with institutions for HCPs, perinatal epidemiologists, data access providers, and regulators; engage with research

networks e.g. VAC4EU, SIGMA, EU PE&PV and initiatives such as the European Health Data Space. The team is thinking of setting up the Real-World Evidence for Europe Alliance (RWE4EU) as a voice for transforming RWD into reliable evidence through a harmonized strategy focusing on the expertise of global members. This would function in the form of a Consortium, which is currently being defined by the UMCU legal department.

For the PowerPoint presentation, please see Annex 1 (page 25-28).

Recommendations, comments and questions from the Advisory Board

- **Piasecki:** What does people readiness entail? **A:** The ConcePTION consortium consists of 88 partners, showcasing significant readiness among its members. After the project's completion, our goal is to retain these organizations and attract others who are interested in joining our efforts. Conducting a study requires substantial time and a diverse team of skilled professionals. Therefore, it is essential to train them to ensure a harmonized approach.

3. Work Stream 3: Breastmilk Study/Lactation Network

Building on the learnings from the ConcePTION initiative, which focused primarily on pregnancy, pragmatic and sustainable solutions were identified for ecosystem-wide capacity building. Now, the aim shifts the focus more towards breastfeeding. Milk4Baby will utilize the insights that were gained in ConcePTION to create a project at the European level, involving various stakeholders. The team foresees future regulatory incentives for information on medication safety, and Milk4Baby would be an excellent tool to meet these new requirements, especially as it is easier to change labelling in the breastfeeding domain than in the pregnancy domain.

The approach will involve recruitment and sampling, focusing on collecting milk samples rather than data. These samples will be stored for analysis to extract valuable bioanalytical information. Once evidence has been gathered, this needs to be disseminated effectively to the appropriate stakeholders. Through the ConcePTION experience, the team learned that a mono-centric approach to recruitment does not fit every drug, and diverse needs need to be addressed with a systematic sampling strategy, possibly through milk banks. Although large systematic sampling is a powerful idea, it requires significant time and resources.

The Milk4baby ecosystem consists of four pillars: 1. Recruitment and sampling, 2. Storage, 3. Bio analytics and nonclinical pharmacometrics methods, and 4. Dissemination and information:

1. Recruitment and sampling: Having access to samples and carrying out measurements is crucial. Within the network, the aspiration is to create a European-wide sample depository for systematic sampling to minimize the loss of opportunity, as well as launching investigator-initiated studies.
2. Storage: High quality storage should be guaranteed. As centralizing all samples in one European location is costly, the team proposes a more cost-effective distributed storage approach.
3. Bio analytics and nonclinical pharmacometrics methods: WS3 hopes to further develop methods for innovative sampling, such as dry blood and milk and smaller volumes to quantify both infant exposure and maternal blood, and validation of the PBPK/popPK models. The team

are starting to develop a decision tree for methodological approaches for the question at hand, depending on the compound and the amount of data available. Translating the information that is gathered into actionable insights, such as label change.

4. Dissemination and information: For dissemination, identifying various communication channels is essential to achieve impact and allow for label change.

Moving forward, WS3 will need to consolidate the work, publish the outputs, and identify potential funding sources. WS3 will also be connecting with the European Network of milk banks, biobanks, enrolment centers, and bioanalytical platforms, as potential partners. Securing funders' commitment is vital for further development of these methods.

For the PowerPoint presentation, please see Annex 1 (page 28-34).

Recommendations, comments and questions from the Advisory Board

- **Chambers:** It is a remarkable initiative and a necessary one. Are you trying to address storage conditions in biobanks methodologically? For instance, does it matter per drug if they are in the biobank for over 10 years? There would be potential opportunities for international collaboration to look at these issues. **A:** That would be interesting. Depending on the drug and the type of sample, sometimes we are too optimistic, and it is better to have this sense of urgency and to try to analyse samples as soon as feasible. **Sturkenboom:** This has been an incredible effort leading to filling a gap in Europe in this regard, for both *in vivo*, *in vitro*, the minipig model, deep sampling human lactation and moving onto a population-based approach. International collaboration would be highly beneficial.
- **Straus:** You mention pharmaco-epidemiology data based on registry. Would you be solely collecting milk samples? **A:** Initially, this will involve gathering information, focusing on both plasma and milk. Our teams are already collecting data through the Meds4Mums2B app, and they continue to follow up with participants. It has been suggested that we invite these women to participate in lactation studies once they have given birth.

4. Work Stream 4: MUMS & E-Learning

MUMS is a free to use publicly accessible knowledge bank with reliable and up-to-date information on the use of medicines in pregnancy. The current version does not yet include lactation data, but the team is aiming to do so. It is targeted primarily at countries that do not have an already trusted resource. Currently, the prototype includes 40 medications, with plans of extension to over 200, and five maternal medical conditions (depression, epilepsy, multiple sclerosis, rheumatoid arthritis, and Systemic Lupus Erythematosus).

The information on the website is a combination of information from existing European knowledge banks, which was combined after doing a review with the knowledge group team. The writing teams do not conduct literature reviews. The information on the website for each medicine includes a lay summary paragraph on the effect of the medicine on a pregnancy, as well as more detailed information meant for the HCP. Each page also includes references, both those used for the text and related articles. The disclaimer on the website most importantly includes that the website is not medical advice.

The team is working on translations to Polish and Italian, which will account for cultural context. Currently, for any other selected language than English, the website refers the reader to the countries' knowledge bank/trusted provider.

The e-learning package is based on a systematic approach supported by learning technologists and academics who are knowledgeable about the learning outcomes and curve for under- and postgraduate students. The learning package, consisting of 10 modules, is currently under review by EECCME for accreditation. All modules include an introduction, tests throughout the module, and many visual and interactive elements.

The e-learning space is currently hosted by Elevate and will be moving towards a sustainable solution. The team is working out a collaboration between ENTIS and Irish Medicines and Pregnancy Service to host the content on behalf of ENTIS under a service level agreement. Additionally, the Royal College of Surgeons in Ireland is willing to host in their environment. After EECCME accreditation, the IRCS will assess it to their own standards and include assessment criteria appropriate for their courses. Ideally, IRCS will host the e-learning on behalf of ENTIS and do a proof of concept with pharmacy undergraduates in the next academic term. Simultaneously, the team will be working on a roadmap for getting wider accessibility for additional disciplines and at postgraduate level, as well as getting funding to sustain it all.

For the PowerPoint presentation, please see Annex 1 (page 34-38).

Recommendations, comments and questions from the Advisory Board

- **Conover:** Mother2Baby offers numerous fact sheets that are used worldwide, also in Spanish. They ensure that translators have expertise in teratology. Other fact sheets, like LactMed®, are available in English and could be translated through collaboration with others. **A:** Mother2Baby is a valuable resource for cross-referencing in MUMS. MUMS collaborates with the TISs to review this information and messaging.
- **Conover:** What we have seen is that it is possible. The main expense will be the translations and updates. We do the updates routinely every two years, and if there are major changes.
- **Chambers:** In PRGLAC, one of our fifteen recommendations is providing better dissemination of information on pregnancy and lactation safety to the public and providers. Are you planning on including lactation data in the future and will you consider translating the information provided in LactMed and/or the LactRx app? The only issue might be that this data is not geared to the public, but solely to healthcare providers, but it is already there, paid for and maintained by the National Institutes of Health. **A:** That is a wonderful suggestion, and such collaboration could help sustain our platform.
- **Conover** shares that she is willing to provide additional content for the e-learning platform from her own courses.

5. Work Stream 5-6: Communication, Advocacy & Public Private Alliance

IMI ConcePTION, which began in 2019, is one of the largest consortia at IHI, aiming to build a system that generates better data on medicine safety during pregnancy and lactation, ensuring this information reaches stakeholders for evidence-based decisions. Annually, there are about 5 million pregnancies in

the EU, and while most women prefer to avoid medicine during pregnancy, it's sometimes unavoidable. Proper evidence about medicines is lacking, with many inconsistencies in the available information. Over the past five years, our work has focused on developing methods, generating evidence and creating a system to disseminate this information.

This is where the alliance comes into play: there is a big problem that needs to be solved and ConcePTION has been working on the solution to that problem. But there is still no regulatory infrastructure or policy related to this issue. Therefore, the alliance sets out the following goal: create understanding and recognition from regulatory authorities that this problem exists and that our methodology can solve the problem. It is of great importance that we move this forward, and do not lose what has been accomplished over the years, and this can only be done if the partners continue to work together in the form of an alliance.

The alliance has three core aims: 1. **Champion** the need for reliable and robust data, 2. **Advocate** the need for dedicated oriented policies and incentives, and 3. **Galvanize** our collective efforts.

For the alliance, WS5-6 is envisioning a structure similar to the Consortium: it should foster collaboration while avoiding hierarchical relationships. The alliance is a network of networks, open to partners outside the current Consortium. With the alliance comes the involvement in working groups focused on specific topics, which will be defined based on needs and interests. There will be no engagement of the alliance in data generation. The study networks and resources are not a formal part of the alliance, and they will be governed separately.

As for the governance of the alliance, it will be steered by a steering committee in which all the members have one equal vote. Those who become a member will have the chance to be in the driving seat to shape the agenda for the work plan of the alliance. As for the membership fee, this has not yet been concretized. WS5-6 currently suggests a two-tiered membership plan for pharma and others.

For the PowerPoint presentation, please see Annex 1 (page 13-18).

Recommendations, comments and questions from the Advisory Board

- **Chambers:** The initiative is a commendable evolution of your work with ConcePTION. Notably, the [BRIDGE](#) (Empowering Women Living with Chronic Disease) initiative, which operates on a global scale and involves pharmaceutical companies, patients, and other stakeholders, shares similar objectives, particularly in supporting women with chronic diseases. Their formal launch took place last month. This underscores the importance of a global alliance, and advancing this is crucial for the mitigation of regulatory barriers.
- **Conover:** Another initiative, that I am a part of is CAMT (Coalition to Advance Maternal Therapeutics) which is advocating for regulatory change and protecting women by involving them in research rather than excluding them. It would be worthwhile to connect.
- **Conover:** In the realm of conveying information and health literacy, there is significant overlap with Mother2Baby, which offers numerous fact sheets. These resources don't need to be created from scratch, there can be potential overlap and collaboration.

- **Chambers:** Little progress is being made on implementing solutions and closing the gap in our field in the United States due issues similar as those faced by ConcePTION, such as the question of authority and resources. Timing is crucial, especially in the light of the overturn of Roe v. Wade currently in the United States. There is no better time than now. Aligning with United States’ national initiatives, such as [PRGLAC](#) (Task Force on Research Specific to Pregnant Women and Lactating Women), would be an excellent opportunity to address these challenges. PRGLAC is primarily funded by the National Institute of Child Health and Human Development and has representation from all key government agencies, including the Food and Drug Authority.

Annex 1 – PowerPoint Presentation

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SAFETY EVIDENCE ECOSYSTEM

Scientific Advisory Board Meeting July 2024

efpia

The research leading to these results has received support from the EU/EFPIA Innovative Medicines Initiative (IMI) Joint Undertaking
ConcePTION grant n° 821520

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Agenda

1. Welcome – *Miriam Sturkenboom*
2. Work Stream 5-6: Communication, Advocacy & Public-Private Alliance – *Jasper Levink*
3. Work Stream 1: Pregnancy Study Network – Primary Data - *Rebecca Bromley*
4. Work Stream 2: Pregnancy Study Network – Secondary Data – *Miriam Sturkenboom*
5. Work Stream 3: Breastmilk Study/Lactation Network – *Pieter Annaert*
6. Work Stream 4: MUMS & E-learning – *Stéphanie Tcherny-Lessenot & Brian Cleary*
7. Closing – *Miriam Sturkenboom*

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WS5&6: Communication, Advocacy & Public-Private Alliance

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innovative
medicines
initiative

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concePTION

IMI ConcePTION: a force for change

- We launched in April 2019 to build an eco-system to generate the information we require.
- We are a consortium of over **80 public and private sector organisations** from academia, regulatory agencies, and industry.
- We are funded by the EC's Innovative Medicines Initiative (IMI).

Our mission is to empower and enable those pregnant and breastfeeding to make potentially life-changing decisions easily, so reducing the considerable burden on our healthcare systems.

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initiative

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The facts show we have a problem to solve.

SOURCES

- Deane J, Raikley GE, Grayson DL, Morgan SG. Fetal protein drug use during pregnancy in developed countries: A systematic review. *Pharmacoepidemiology and Drug Safety*. 2011.
- Mosley JFZ rd, Smith LL, Dezan MO, Harm Frost (Gardes), Argueta B. Assessing the information in the Summaries of Product Characteristics for the use of medicines in pregnancy and lactation. 2015;13(2):605.
- Br J Clin Pharmacol. doi:10.1111/bcp.12315. 2015;79(2):327-344.
- UK General Practitioner survey, 2020.

To date, our work has focused in these key areas:

1 Building a system that generates urgently needed evidence reliably.

By establishing and validating the methods needed to use existing data about the use and effects of medicines in pregnancy and when breastfeeding.

Resulting in these **STUDY NETWORKS**:

- Primary data collection
- Secondary use of EHR data
- Lactation studies

2 Summarising and disseminating key information consistently and convincingly.

By developing the MUMS knowledge bank to guide and advise those who are pregnant or breastfeeding and their healthcare professionals.

Resulting in these **RESOURCES**:

- E-learning
- Drug safety information (MUMS)
- Breastmilk biobank*

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Significantly, we have the data and the essential elements of a system to capture and analyse it reliably.

However, the system is not used effectively, as the policy and regulatory infrastructure is not in place to mandate the collection of the data we need.

Only by continuing to work together, can we break this cycle of neglect.

The Alliance is committed to three core aims:

Champion

The need for robust and reliable data and evidence on the safe use of medicines during pregnancy and when breastfeeding.

Advocate

The need for dedicated pregnancy and lactation-oriented policies and incentives, including the Paediatric Investigation Plan (PIP) and Paediatric Study Plan (PSP).

Galvanise

Our collective efforts to further develop the tools and platforms we need to generate and disseminate vital insights.

The vision

The ConcePTION Alliance

We envision an alliance structured similarly to a consortium, one that fosters collaboration and avoids hierarchical relationships.

It will provide a global, transparent, independent, and non-competitive platform, where members can exchange ideas, develop potentially ground-breaking partnerships, and build a shared agenda and work plan.

The model: A network of networks

■ Current ConcePTION partners
■ New opportunities

Whether your organisation is a pharma company, academic institution, regulatory body, or patient support group, it can benefit in two ways:

1
You can help shape a new environment that ensures that those pregnant and breastfeeding are no longer denied what we see as a fundamental human right.

2
You can help build greater trust with society and enhance the reputation of your organisation in doing so. You also gain access to a network of leading experts in safe medicine use during pregnancy and breastfeeding.

The benefits

Membership

Membership will include:

- The invite to attend regular meetings aimed at advancing each of the three core aims, including agenda setting and topic prioritization.
- Involvement (as much as possible) in dedicated working groups on specific topics, depending on the need and interests.
- Agreement with the principles that will be jointly defined in a governance document.

We are still finalising the fee structure. We expect a two-tier membership for pharma as well as other organisations. Alliance membership won't include automatic access to all study networks, we will provide further registration details soon.

Governance

- Governed by an independent steering committee in which all members are represented.
- Different interests will be given an appropriate weighting within the governance structure, which is independent of financial contribution.
- The Alliance will not be engaged in evidence generation.

Get on board!

Any organisation committed to breaking this historic cycle of neglect can join. By being part of the ConcePTION Alliance, your organisation will be playing a big part in building the future.

So, please adopt our mission as your own and help make the safer use of medicines during pregnancy and when breastfeeding a reality. **Both now and for the generations that follow.**

Work Stream 1: Pregnancy Study Network - Primary Data

Neurodevelopmental Outcomes

¹ Bluett-Duncan et al., In Preparation. ² Bromley et al., 2023 Frontiers in Pharmacology

Introducing the LIFETIME framework

Why?

- Stakeholders identified the importance of neurodevelopmental outcomes.
- Few surveillance initiatives include neurodevelopmental follow up.
- Stakeholders identified barriers including
 - Lack of expertise
 - Cost of follow up.

How?

- Create an expert collaborative network.
- Introduce a standardised framework of longitudinal follow up.
- Developed shared protocols and legal agreements to combine data.
- Expands pharmacovigilance scope to include neurodevelopmental assessments as routine.

Who?

- Developed by a team of experts in child development, clinical genetics, teratology pharmacovigilance, statistics, and epidemiology.
- Delivered through a collaborative expert network of centres across Europe.

Introducing the LIFETIME framework

LIFETIME in practice

Long-term investigation following exposure to individual medicines in utero: **the LIFETIME system**

*Must meet minimum dataset requirements

There are two levels of investigation:

- 1

Screening Level:
 Cost-effective method for assessing large populations using parent-reported outcomes via validated questionnaires in their native language. Ideal for surveillance initiatives with a high annual volume of participant registrations.
- 2

Enhanced Level:
 Utilises blinded, researcher-led assessments using an established protocol to deliver confirmatory evidence.

 High measurement sensitivity means it requires fewer participants, making this in-depth approach ideal for studying new or rarely used medications.

*Must meet minimum dataset requirements
 ** Only a small number of sites in the network are required for this aspect

LIFETIME pilot network

Our progress so far...

- **Utilized** LIFETIME framework in 4 European centres.
- **Recruited** 1,200+ mother-child pairs.
- **Standardized** data collection for medication use and maternal health data.
- **Initiated** framework expansion: Pilot centres plan to adopt LIFETIME (screening or enhanced).
- **Attracted** interest from new centres wishing to join.

LIFETIME offers five key benefits:

- 1 Proactive pharmacovigilance for early detection of potential risk
- 2 Standardised data collection across countries
- 3 Screening and confirmatory data collection running in parallel
- 4 Investigation of medication exposures via breastfeeding
- 5 Ability to build in additional sub cohort investigations

The research leading to these results has received support from the EU/EFPIA Innovative Medicines Initiative [2] Joint Undertaking ConcePTION grant n° 821520

Next Steps...

- 1 Develop specifically for antiseizure medications
- 2 Develop for general pharmacovigilance initiatives

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- **Address** data gap in long-term child health & neurodevelopment following exposure *in utero*.
- **Build** a comprehensive dataset of Mother-child participants utilising LIFETIME Framework.
- **Extend** role out of the enhanced investigation for ASMs.
- **Report** findings to patient, health professional, regulator and industry stakeholders.
- **Fund** further utilisation via a multi-faceted set of stakeholders.

Our priorities

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Questions

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Work Stream 2: ConcePTION EHR

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How data, people, infrastructure and methods combine for sustainability

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Our achievements so far...

Use of ConcePTION pipeline accepted as method

ConcePTION Tools wiki

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Our key priorities:

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Our priority connections

- **Pregnant and lactating women: liaise for social license to analyse data & needs**
- **Institutions:**
 - Healthcare professionals: train to use the ecosystem and understand needs.
 - Perinatal epidemiologists: expertise for study design, conduct & interpretation.
 - Data scientists & statisticians: engage and train for robust and reliable data transformation.
 - Data access providers: create data readiness on global level.
 - Regulators: create mandate to generate evidence on medicines safety in pregnancy.
- **Research Networks:**
 - Collaboration with networks using ConcePTION CDM to synergize (e.g. VAC4EU, SIGMA, EU PE&PV)
- **Initiatives:**
 - European Health Data Space

Real World Evidence for Europe Alliance:

A voice on how to transform RWD into reliable evidence through a harmonized strategy focusing on the expertise of members:

Commit: Our fuse

- UMCU ready to coordinate and support the ConcePTION EHR network with CHUT
- Consortium agreement with governance structure will be prepared by UMCU and sent to institutions who want to join
- Research Institutions & Data access providers across the globe may become part of the ConcePTION-EHR network by signing the consortium agreement.
- We will work with Dialogue to make materials
- Organize collaboration with VAC4EU, SIGMA & EU PE&PV
- Participate in ConcePTION Alliance

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ConcePTION grant n° 821520

Work Stream 3: Milk4Baby

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Prof. Pieter Annaert

Drug Delivery and Disposition Lab
Chair of the KU Leuven Department of
Pharmaceutical and Pharmacological Sciences
CSO at BioNotus - Belgium

- Milk4baby team

Who we are

Investigators

- **Dr Jasper Levink**, sustainability adviser, ConcePTION
- **Dr PD Monia Guidi**, pharmacometrician, UNIL, CH
- **Dr PD Ursula Winterfeld**, head of Swiss Teratogen Information Service (STIS) - Information center for Drugs in pregnancy and breastfeeding, CH
- **Dr Vera Mitter**, head applied Research and Development Midwifery, Bern University of Applied Sciences, CH
- **Prof. Anne Smits**, **Prof. Karel Allegaert**, neonatologists, University Hospitals Leuven, and KU Leuven, Belgium
- **Pharm Johan Van Daele**, xenobiotics quantification in milk, BioNotus, Belgium
- **Dr Rebecca Bromley**, pediatric neuropsychologist, University of Manchester, UK
- **Prof Sue Jordan**, real-world data, Swansea University, UK
- **Colleagues representing 10 University hospitals through Europe**

Where are we ?

- **identified pragmatic and sustainable solutions** for key challenges in the process of risk assessment, sampling, sample storage, data generation and impact analysis of transfer of medicines from mother to infant, and tested those solutions in small-scale pilots.
- **a clear vision of the conditions required for ecosystem-wide capacity building** to radically and rapidly reduce uncertainty about the safe use of medications during breastfeeding.

Our solution: - Milk4baby

- **Milk4baby, an ecosystem-wide capacity building** of public and private stakeholders, breastfeeding women, and researchers to generate and disseminate timely and reliable evidence on drug transfer into human milk and the long-term outcomes for children exposed to medication during breastfeeding.
- **Milk4baby, a follow-up project developed in conjunction with WP3-WP4 and industrial partners to go from small scale pilots to change of label.**

Why do we need the Milk4Baby ecosystem?

- **Progress in Drug safety** in pregnancy more advanced than drug safety in breastfeeding.
- **Planning for future regulatory incentives** for information on medication safety for breastfed infants (e.g. EMA consultation).
- ConcePTION taught us pragmatic and sustainable solutions through a proof-of-concept exercise.
- **Time to go from small scale pilots to change of label.**

The Milk4baby ecosystem

- **Answer various needs** (post marketing and premarketing clinical studies, validation studies for nonclinical approaches, ...)
 - **Systematic sampling** to prevent loss of opportunity and create a European wide sample depository,
 - **Network to launch investigator-initiated studies** using already running lactation studies initiative.

- **Build European capacity** generating a centralized databank for clinical samples related information with a European wide disseminated storage.

Further develop Bioanalytics, (non)clinical and pharmacometrics methods

- Bioanalytics aligned with innovative sampling strategy to quantify infant exposure and maternal blood (e.g. dry blood/milk; small volumes; multiplex methods; biomarkers in milk)
- Bioanalytics standards for label change (GLP – GCP-GC(L)P)
- Decision tree for methodological approach
- Further development, validation and application of bottom-up and top-down computational models (PBPK / popPK)
- collect pharmacoepi data through an app based registry

- **Allow a change of label** through EMA assessment for scientific guidance to support the qualification procedure of the process (leverage lessons learned WP3 EMA QA expedition)
- **Dissemination of information**
 - o Identification of communication channels
 - o Implementation of processes allowing label changes
 - o Create dissemination processes with MUMs and other information knowledge banks

Moving forward

Consolidate
What still needs to happen before the end of the project?

- Publish wp3 and wp4 output to consolidate our expertise
- Identification of potential Funding bodies (new IMI call)

Connect
Who do we need to build relationships with to sustain progress?

- European Network of milk bank, biobanks, enrolment centres and bioanalytical platforms willing to specialized in medication quantification in breast milk.
- We are reaching out to:
 - EMBA
 - BBMRI
 - University Hospitals
 - Bioanalytics partners

Commit
What do we need in terms of commitments to continue our work?

- Funders commitment (new IMI call) to develop Milk4baby
- Clients willing to use Milk4baby (industrial partners, regulatory entities, academic partners, ...)

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**Work Stream 4:
MUMS & e-learning**

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Introducing the MUMS* Knowledge Bank

- **Free-to-use, publicly accessible** bank of reliable, up-to-date information about use of medication during pregnancy and lactation.
- Developed **in conjunction with ENTIS**.
- Targeted primarily at countries and languages that **do not already have a trusted national online resource**.
- Initial prototype includes **40 medications**, with plans to extend **to over 200**.

*Mothers Using Medicines Safely

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 conception

Great news!

June 13th 2024 the website is launched:

www.MUMS.eu

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 conception

Let's take a look!

www.MUMS.eu

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Moving forward

Consolidate
What still needs to happen before the end of the project?

- Get feedback on the prototype
- Finalize communication plan
- Translate into Polish and Italian
- Take appropriate legal actions for MUMS after 31 Dec 2024

Connect
Who do we need to build relationships with to sustain progress?

- Stakeholder event in preparation.
- Targeted participants:
 - Health professional and women's organisation through leaders
 - Neutral experts regarding the "market" situation in a country, possible collaborators or competing initiatives
 - National funding decision makers eg. from a health ministry or health insurer
 - Trans-national funders and sponsors eg. WHO, Gates Foundation, EC
 - Sustainability advisors (IHI, EIT Health)

Commit
What do we need in terms of commitments to continue our work?

Obtain funding to:

- Continue as a free-to-use service from 2025 onwards
- Keep existing content up-to-date
- Increase to 200 medicines (our MVP)
- Translate into all required languages.

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Brian Cleary

Chief Pharmacist, Rotunda Hospital,
Dublin, Ireland

The HCP e-learning

Royal College of Surgeons in Ireland (RCSI) has agreed to host and pilot use of the e-Learning package with undergraduate Pharmacy students in the next academic year.

Moving forward

Consolidate
What still needs to happen before the end of the project?

- Submit EACCME application and COI forms.
- Review against RCSI standards.
- Develop assessment materials (MCQs and OSCEs).
- Potentially film case-based scenarios.

Connect
Who do we need to build relationships with to sustain progress?

- RCSI will host the material on behalf of the Irish Medicines in Pregnancy Service (IMPS) – SLA between ENTIS and IMPS required to ensure authors consent to their content being used by ENTIS.
- Need to establish a roadmap for wider accessibility.

Commit
What do we need in terms of commitments to continue our work?

- Explore sustainability funding/revenue generation options for ongoing hosting and wider availability of the eLearning package
- Engage internationally to start multidisciplinary undergraduate and postgraduate engagement with eLearning package.

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